

**IN NETWORKS OF INFOCOMMUNICATION OBJECTS
USER INFORMATION INFORMATION INFORMATION SECURITY
CLASSIFICATION OF METHODS AND MEANS OF SUPPLY**

Ulugbek Khujayevich Mingboev

Jizzakh branch of National University of Uzbekistan.Docent

ulugbekmingboyev@gmail.com

Alijon Abdurasul o'g'li Abdurasulov

Jizzakh branch of National University of Uzbekistan.Master degree

alijon.abdurasulov@bk.ru

ABSTRACT

This article provides information on how to determine a number of parameters for networks of infocommunication objects user information information security, informatization tools and systems.

Keywords. *Information security, infocommunication objects, information attack, network equipment, international security, object of information attacks, information support, cybersecurity.*

INTRODUCTION. Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, favorable conditions are being created for the introduction of modern information technologies, computer equipment and telecommunications into all spheres of society, their use, further satisfaction of the growing demand and needs of Citizens for information, access to the world Information Society, and expansion of the use of World Information Resources. One of the important issues is the protection of electronic data exchangers on computer networks and the establishment of a protected channel for the exchange of confidential information on networks [1].

During the development of the Internet, electronic communications of individual and corporate users were formed. The Internet has provided access to particularly individual individuals as well. The merger of National, personal and corporate computer networks into a single Internet network gave a solid impetus to the development of network services, and it had a significant impact on the development and strengthening of the electronic service business.

One of the important issues is the protection of electronic data exchanged on computer networks from intruders and the establishment of an autonomous channel for the exchange of confidential information on networks [2].

METHODS. One of the main methods conditions for the widespread use of the internet has been and will remain to provide the same level of security for all transactions conducted through it. This applies to information transmitted between users, information stored in databases of trading systems, information attached to financial transactions.

RESULTS. The concept results of Information Security is defined as the state of tolerance of accidental or deliberate influences that eliminate the unacceptable risks to the destruction, degradation and exposure of information that cause material damage to information owners or users of information. The importance of these methods is very high as the network is completely open to access from outside. The great importance of security factors is determined by the large number of studies conducted on the Internet.

DISCUSSION. Ensuring information security in Computer Networks is the technical, software and cryptographic methods and tools in preventing users from owning network elements and reserves without permission, as well as organizational events are told

Methods for ensuring information security can be classified into 4 main classes:

1. Organizational and legal methods;

Organizational and legal methods of information security include organizational and legal methods. Organizational measures should include a list of behaviors and

requirements that govern the procedure for organizing, forming, using and engaging legal entities and individuals in the support of Public Information Resources. The basis of legal methods is made up of laws that provide for the processing and transmission of information, compliance with the rules of their use. [3]. Engineering and technical methods of information security are carried out on the basis of electronic and electronic-mechanical devices that apply to the technical means of the computer, perform certain functions of Information Security independently or as part of a complex with software tools. In the work activities of organizations, a huge number of devices are used, from telephone apparatus to automated systems.

In a computer network, it is possible to include protected cryptoprotocols above all in software protection methods. When these protocols are used, there is an opportunity to reliably protect the connection. Another class of software protection methods from remote attack include existing applications today. Software methods of Information Protection are carried out only with the help of special programs that are designed to ensure the security of information and are included in the software of computer tools.

In computer networks, cryptographic methods are used to solve the problem of Information Security. Cryptography is a science of data security.

Modern cryptography is a field of knowledge that addresses the problems of information security in confidentiality, integrity, authentication, and the inability of parties to deny authorship. The provision of confidentiality is understood as the protection of this information from persons who do not have the right to access information.

CONCLUSION. The problem of ensuring the confidentiality of a message transmitted by a communication channel controlled by an opponent is one of the traditional issues of cryptography.

Ensuring integrity is understood as a guarantee that information cannot be changed without permission. To guarantee integrity, there must be a simple and reliable criterion that determines whether to make any changes to the data. These changes can

be made by deleting text, replacing it, putting a new one. Ensuring authentication refers to the development of methods for confirming the information itself and the authenticity of the parties in the process of informational interaction. The source of information transmitted over the communication channel must be authenticated with the date of creation, the data of the organizer, the date of transmission and so on. [4].

REFERENCES

1. Decree No. 27 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on approval of the concept of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures to implement it”(November 29, 2021).
2. The law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Cybersecurity“(OORQ–764, 15.04.2022.)
3. Abdumalikov A.A. A study of static and dynamic characteristics of multifunctional signal converters // International scientific and technical journal. “Chemical Technology. Control And Managment” Tashkent. ISSN: 1815-4840, E-ISSN 2181-1105. Volume -2020. Issue 4(94). -P.38-45
4. Mingboyev Ulugbek and Abdurasulov Alijon, “Information security monitoring”, IJCSTR, pp. 275-279, May 2023.